

INFLUENCE OF CULTURAL AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC BACKGROUND ON PERSONALITY PATTERN OF MISHING ADOLESCENTS IN LAKHIMPUR DISTRICTS OF ASSAM

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1. INTRODUCTION:

North eastern region of India comprises the Seven Sisters States of Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland and Tripura. It covers 7.76% of the country's total geographical area of 32,87,240 sq. km. The North East India lies between latitudes 22 and 29.5 and longitudes 89.70' and 97.30'E. According to 2001 census, the total population in entire North-East India is 3, 85 core out of which the scheduled tribe population is 1.06 core. In words, the scheduled tribes constituted 27.42% of the total population N.E.R.

There are many scheduled tribes, scheduled caste, OBC, MOBC, general etc. in the state of Assam. Assam alone account for 3% of the total scheduled tribe population of the North-East. According to the Scheduled Caste and Scheduled Tribes others (Amendment) Act, 2002 there are, 25 scheduled tribes in Assam.

Keywords: Personality, Mishing, Adolescent, Assam, NER , Psychological

1.2 Adolescence: Adolescence is the process of developing from a child into on a youth. The term adolescence has a broader meaning. It includes mental, emotional and social maturity as well as physical maturity. This point of view has been expressed by piaget (1983 p-121) said- Psychologically, adolescence is the age when the individual became integrated into the society of adults, the age when the child no longer feels that he is below the level of his elders but equal, at least in right. This integration into adult society has many affective aspects; more or less linked with puberty's it also includes very profound intellectual changes..... These intellectual transformations typical of the adolescents thinking enable him not only to achieve his integration into the social relationship of adults, which is, in fact, the most general characteristic of this period of development.

1.3 Personality and personality pattern: The term "Personality" comes from the Latin word 'Persona', meaning "mask". Among the ancient Greeks, the actors wore masks to hide their identity and enable them to represent the characters they were depicting in the play. This dramatic technique was later adopted by the Romans and from them we get our modern term 'Personality'.

Human personality has long been a subject of exploration, discussion and transformation. Personality is a set of particular qualities as makes the individual who has it distinct and conspicuous among his associates. That is the real basis of what we call vaguely personality. From this it is clear that personality may developed through there are persons who believe that there is no such thing. Eysneck its (1971) "personality with gives a complete picture of the human behaviors patterns by including cognitive, affective and somatic aspects "personality is the more and less stable and enduring organization of a person character, temperament, intellect and physique, which determine his unique adjustment to the environment".

Cattell R.B (1970) "Personality" is that which permits a prediction what a person will do in a given situation".

1.4 Socio economic and cultural status: Socio economic status continues to be one of the important determinants of educational achievement. It is also a fact that in the area of psychological performances, Sociological Advancements and cultural development, the role of Socio-economic status is an effective one

Level Socioeconomic status, cultural context and Academic are the three most prominent factors that impact an individual’s growth and development. Each separate component is very closely linked in our everyday lives; touching and molding who we become.

Socioeconomic status (SES), also referred to as social class, plays a major role in human growth and development. SES is an economic and sociological combined total measure of a person’s work experience and of an individual’s or family’s economic or social position in relation to others. SES can influence a person’s education level, quality of health care, diet, place of residence, even stress levels

Culture is a system of beliefs, values, languages, and behaviours, and human-made aspects of the physical environment, that varies from one group to another. These variations can have powerful effects on adolescent development.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To study the Culture and Socio-economic background of Mishing Adolescents.
2. To assess influence of culture and Socio-economic background on Personality pattern, of Mishing Adolescents

2.1 Methodology:

The research study on tribal community of Mishing Adolescents in Assam, as a field survey of an exploratory nature. It was a sample survey data based research conducted in the Lakhimpur District of Assam. Data were collected on the levels of Personality Pattern, Culture and Socio-Economic Background of Mishing adolescents with the use of various standardized and self developed tools.

2.2 Tools for the study: -

- (i.) Multidimensional personality Inventory (M.P.I.) standardized by K.M. Manju Agarwal(1984).
- (ii.) Culture and socio-economic background questionnaire developed by the investigator

2.3 Delimitation:-

The study was confined to the adolescents’ students of ixth the and x th standard age group of 13 to 16 yrs. The study will comprise 250 Mishing students from Lakhimpur District only. Study will be conducted both boys and girls students of Mishing.

3. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATIONS OF DATA:

Table-3.1

Influence of cultural and socio-economic background on personality pattern of Mishing Adolescents in Lakhimpur district (Block-wise)

Personal ity Patterns	Soci o- Eco	Karunabari Block (N= Low-0 High-45)	Bihpuria Block (N= Low-8 High-52)	NowboichaBlock (N= Low-3 High-30)	Narayanpur Block (N= Low-4 High-35)
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	nom ic	Me an	sd	t	df	Sig (2 tail)	Me an	sd	T	df	Sig (2 tail)	Me an	sd	T	df	Sig (2 tail)	Me an	Sd	t	df	Sig (2 tail)
Extrover sion	Low	.	.				38. 88	4.1 5	.24 5	8	.80	42. 67	13. 05	.28 3	1	.77	48. 00	9.2 3	3.0 1	3 7	.00
	Introver sion	High	39. 98	7.6 6			39. 27	4.1 7				40. 90	9.9 3				38. 69	5.4 4			
Self Concept	Low	.	.				39. 50	4.9 8	.24 5	8	.80	37. 00	6.2 4	.53 3	1	.59	43. 50	9.8 1	1.6 8	3 7	.10
	High	43. 38	7.5 2				39. 08	4.4 5				39. 70	8.5 2				39. 23	4.0 6			
Depend ent Indepen dent	Low	.	.				47. 38	3.4 6	.72 5	8	.47	49. 33	6.0 2	.22 3	1	.82	48. 00	8.0 8	.24 3	3 7	.81
	High	46. 36	6.4 3				45. 54	6.9 9				50. 47	8.5 0				47. 20	6.0 5			
Temper ament	Low	.	.				39. 50	3.8 5	.99 5	8	.32	46. 67	8.9 6	1.5 3	1	.13	39. 50	5.1 9	- 1	3 7	.51
	High	42. 98	6.5 8				41. 75	6.2 1				39. 10	8.1 7				41. 31	5.2 0			
Adjustm ent	Low	.	.				50. 25	4.0 2	.47 5	8	.64	50. 33	8.6 2	.08 3	1	.93	53. 50	4.0 4	.52 0	3 7	.60
	High	46. 98	7.2 0				49. 00	7.3 2				50. 73	7.3 6				51. 71	6.6 7			
Anxiety	Low	.	.				37. 75	4.8 6	.31 5	8	.75	40. 33	.57	.19 3	1	.84	41. 50	.57	1.2 4	3 7	.22
	High	41. 44	7.7 0				38. 25	4.1 4				39. 60	6.3 9				38. 86	4.1 8			

Significant level is at $P < 0.05$

N.B- All Mishing Adolescents followed by 100% high traditional culture

It is observed from the table no 3.1 in the Karunabari Block of Lakhimpur district, no respondents followed by Low Socio- Economic Background groups and 45 sample of High Socio Economic background Group with the Personality Pattern Extroversion Introversion, Mean score is 39.98 with standard diversion 7.66. The Mean score is 43.38 with Standard Deviation 7.52 of High Socio-Economic Background Group (Sample 45) and Personality Pattern Self-Concept.

The Mean score is 46.36 with Standard Deviation 6.43 of High Socio –Economic Background group(45) and Personality Pattern Dependent Independent .

- The Mean Score is 42.98 with Standard Deviation 6.58 of High Socio –Economic Background Group (45) and Personality Pattern Temperament.

- The Mean score is 46.98 with Standard Deviation 7.20 of High Socio –economic background Group (45) and Personality Pattern Adjustment.
- The Mean score is 41.44 with standard deviation 7.70 of High Socio –economic background Group (45) and Personality Pattern Anxiety.

The above table depicts that there exist no significant relation in between High Socio – Economic Background Group with High Traditional Culture of 45 samples and the Personality Patterns like Extroversion Introversion, Self-Concept, Dependent Independent, Temperament, Adjustment, Anxiety of Mishing Adolescents at Karunabari Block in Lakhimpur District.

In the Bihpuria Block of Lakhimpur district, a sample of 8 Low Socio-Economic Background Group and 52 sample of High Socio-Economic Background group with the Personality Pattern Extroversion Introversion, the Mean scores are as 38.88 and 39.27 with standard diversions 4.15 and 4.17, the calculated ‘t’ value is .24 (df- 58, P-.80). It indicate that there is no significant different between Personality pattern of Extroversion introversion with Low and High Socio-economic group.

Low and High Socio-Economic Background Group (sample of 8 and 52) with Personality Pattern Self Concept , The Mean scores are as 39.50 and 39.08 with Standard Deviations are as 4.98 and 4.45, the calculated ‘t’ value is .24(df-58,P-.80).

Low and High Socio-Economic Background Group (sample of 8 and 52) with Personality Pattern Dependent Independent, the Mean scores are as 47.38 and 45.54 with Standard Deviations 3.46 and 6.99, ‘t’ value is .72 (df- 58, P-.47.).

Low and High Socio-Economic Background Group (sample of 8 and 52) with Personality Pattern Temperament , the Mean scores are as 39.50 and 41.75 with Standard Deviations 3.85 and 6.21 ,‘t’ value is .99 (df- 58, P-.32).

Low and High Socio-Economic Background Group (sample of 8 and 52) with Personality Pattern Adjustment, the Mean scores are as 50.25 and 49 with standard deviations 4.02 and 7.32 ,‘t’ value is .47 (df-.58, P-.75).

Low and High Socio-Economic Background Group (sample of 8 and 52) with Personality Pattern Anxiety, the Mean scores are as 37.75 and 38.25 with Standard Deviations 4.86 and 4.14 ,‘t’ value is .31 (df-.58, P-.64).

The above table depicts that there exist no significant relation of Low (sample of 8) and High Socio –Economic Background Group (sample of 52) with High Traditional Culture and the Personality Patterns like Extroversion Introversion, Self-Concept, Dependent Independent, Temperament, Adjustment , Anxiety of Mishing Adolescents at Karunabari Block in Lakhimpur District.

In the Nowboicha Block of Lakhimpur district, a sample of 3 Low socio-economic group and 30 sample of High socio-economic group, the Mean score of Personality Pattern of Extroversion Introversion are as 42.67 and 40.90 with standard diversion are as 13.05 and 9.93. The calculated ‘t’ value is .28 (df- 31, P>0.05)

It indicate that there is no significant different between Personality pattern of Extroversion introversion with Low and High Socio-economic group.

The Mean score of Personality Pattern of Self Concept are as 37.00 and 39.70 with standard diversion are as 6.24 and 8.52 the calculated ‘t’ value is .53 and P>0.05. It indicate that there

is no significant different between Personality pattern of Self Concept and Low and High Socio-economic group.

The Mean score of Personality Pattern of Dependent Independent are as 49.33 and 50.47 with standard diversion are as 6.02 and 8.50 the 't' value is .22 (df- 31, $P>0.05$) It indicates that there exist no significant difference between personality pattern of Dependent Independent and Low and High Socio-economic group.

The Mean Score of Personality Pattern of Temperament are as 46.67 and 39.10 with standard diversion are as 8.96 and 8.17 and 't' value is 1.51 (df- 31, $P>0.05$).

It indicates that there exist no significant difference between personality pattern of Temperament and Low and High Socio-economic Group.

The Mean score of Personality Pattern of Adjustment are as 50.33 and 50.73 with standard diversion are as 8.62 and 7.36 and its 't' value is .08 (df- 31, $P>0.05$). It indicates that there is no significance difference Low and High Socio-economic group.

The Mean score of Personality Pattern of Anxiety are as 40.33 and 39.60 with standard diversion are as .57 and 6.39 the 't' value is .19 (df- 31, $P>0.05$).

It indicates that there exist no significant difference between Personality pattern of Anxiety and Low and High Socio-economic environment group.

In the Narayanpur Block of Lakhimpur district, a sample of 4 Low socio-economic group and 35 sample of High socio-economic group, the Mean score of Personality Pattern of Extroversion Introversion are as 48.00 and 38.69 with standard diversion are as 9.23 and 5.44 The calculated 't' value is 3.01 (df- 37, $P>0.05$)

It depicts that there is no significant different between Personality pattern of Extroversion introversion with Low and High Socio-economic environment group.

The Mean score of Personality Pattern of Self Concept are as 43.50 and 39.23 with standard diversion are as 9.81 and 4.06 the calculated 't' value is 1.68 (df- 37, $P>0.05$)

It depicts that there is no significant different between Personality pattern of Self Concept and Low and High Socio-economic group.

The Mean score of Personality Pattern of Dependent Independent are as 48.00 and 47.20 standard diversion are as 8.08, 6.05 the 't' value is .24 (df- 37, $P>0.05$). It indicates there exist no significant difference between personality pattern of Dependent Independent and Low and High Socio-economic group.

The Mean Score of Personality Pattern of Temperament are as 39.50 and 41.31 with standard diversion are as 5.19 and 5.20 and 't' value is .66 and (df- 37, $P>0.05$). It indicates that there exist no significant difference between personality pattern of Temperament and Low and High Socio-economic Group.

The Mean score of Personality Pattern of Adjustment are as 53.50 and 51.71 with standard diversion are as 5.20 and 4.04 and its 't' value is .52 (df- 37, $P>0.05$). It indicates that there is no significance difference Low and High Socio-economic group.

The Mean score of Personality Pattern of Anxiety are as 41.50 and 38.86 with standard diversion are as .57 and 4.18 the 't' value is 1.24 (df- 37, $P>0.05$). It indicates that there exist no significant difference between Personality pattern of Anxiety and Low and High Socio-economic group.

Table -3.2 cultural and socio-economic background on personality pattern of Mishing Adolescents in Lakhimpur district (Block-wise)

Personality Patterns	Socio-Economic	Karunabari Block (N= Low-0 Average-24)					Bihpuria Block (N= Low-8 Average -22)					NowboichaBlock (N= Low-3 Average -14)					Narayanpur Block (N= Low-4 Average -13)				
		Mean	sd	t	df	Sig (2 tail)	Mean	sd	T	df	Sig (2 tail)	Mean	sd	t	df	Sig (2 tail)	Mean	sd	t	df	Sig (2 tail)
Extroversion	Low	0	.	9.47			38.88	4.15	.24	28	.80	42.67	13.05	1.16	15	.26	48.00	9.23	2.60	15	.02
	Average	24	36.63				38.45	4.09				37.21	6.01				39.85	4.01			
Self Concept	Low	0	.	8.37			39.50	4.98	1.11	28	.27	37.00	6.24	.03	15	.97	43.50	9.81	1.93	15	.07
	Average	24	39.58				37.41	4.36				37.14	6.38				37.08	4.25			
Dependent Independent	Low	0	.	3.81			47.38	3.46	.58	28	.56	49.33	6.02	1.23	15	.23	48.00	8.08	1.31	15	.20
	Average	24	40.50				46.18	5.31				42.43	9.12				43.00	6.21			
Temperament	Low	0	.	7.13			39.50	3.85	.00	28	1.00	46.67	8.96	2.05	15	.05	39.50	5.19	.68	15	.50
	Average	24	40.50				39.50	6.19				36.00	8.01				41.23	4.16			
Adjustment	Low	0	.	5.09			50.25	4.02	.27	28	.78	50.33	8.62	.23	15	.81	53.50	4.04	1.55	15	.14
	Average	24	44.08				50.77	4.70				49.36	6.22				47.85	6.81			
Anxiety	Low	0	.	8.7			37.75	4.86	.20	28	.84	40.33	.57	.64	15	.52	41.50	.57	1.76	15	.09
	Average	24	39.04				38.23	6.04				38.36	5.13				37.38	4.55			

Significant level is at P<0.05

N.B-All Mishing Adolescents followed by 100% high traditional culture

It is observed from the table no 3.2 in the Karunabari Block of Lakhimpur district, no respondents followed by Low Socio economic groups and 24 sample of Average Socio economic group with the personality pattern of Extroversion Introversion, Mean score are 36.63 standard diversions is 9.47

It depicts that there is no significant difference between Personality pattern of Extroversion Introversion and Low socio economic group and Average socio economics group.

The no respondents followed by self-concept and Average with 39.58 mean score and standard diversion is 8.37. With the no calculated 't' value. It indicate that there is no significant different between Personality pattern of Self Concept and Low and Average Socio economic group.

The Mean score of personality pattern of Dependent Independent are as 0 and 40.50 with standard diversion are as 0 and 3.81 With the no calculated 't' value.

It indicates that there exist no significant difference between personality pattern of Dependent Independent and Low and Average Socio -economic group.

The Mean Score of Personality Pattern of Temperament are as 0 and 40.50 with standard diversion are as 0 and 7.13. With the no calculated 't' value. It shows that there exist no significant difference between personality pattern of Temperament and Low and Average Socio -economic Group.

The Mean score of Personality Pattern of Adjustment are as 0 and 44.08 with standard diversion are as 0 and 5.09, with the no calculated 't' value. It indicates that there is no significance difference Low and Average Socio -economic Group..

The Mean score of Personality pattern of Anxiety are as 0 and 39.04 with standard diversion are as 0 and 8.76, with the no calculated 't' value. It indicates that there exist no significant difference between Personality pattern of Anxiety and Low and Average Socio -economic Group.

In the Bihpuria Block of Lakhimpur district, a sample of 8 Low socio-economic groups and 52 sample of Average socio-economic group, the Mean score of Personality pattern of Extroversion Introversion are as 38.88 and 38.45 with standard diversion are as 4.15 and 4.09 The calculated 't' value is .24 (df- 28, $P>0.05$) It indicate that there is no significant different between Personality pattern of Extroversion introversion with Low and Average Socio-economic group.

The Mean score of Personality Pattern of Self Concept are as 39.50 and 37.41 with standard diversion are as 4.98 and 4.36 the calculated 't' value is .111 (df- 28, $P>0.05$) It shows that there is no significant different between Personality pattern of Self Concept and Low and Average Socio-economic group.

The Mean score of personality pattern of Dependent Independent are as 47.38 and 46.18 standard diversion are as 3.46 and 5.31 the 't' value is .72 (df- 28, $P>0.05$) It indicates that there exist no significant difference between personality pattern of Dependent Independent and Low and Average Socio-economic group.

The Mean Score of Personality Pattern of Temperament are as 39.50 and 39.50 with standard diversion are as 3.85 and 6.13 the 't' value is 00 and $P<0.05$. It indicates that there significant difference between personality pattern of Temperament and Low and Average Socio-economic Group.

The Mean score of Personality Pattern of Adjustment are as 50.25 and 50.77 with standard diversion are as 4.02 and 4.70 the 't' value is .27 (df- 28, $P>0.05$). It indicates that there is no significance difference Low and Average Socio-economic group.

The Mean score of Personality pattern of Anxiety are as 37.75 and 38.23 with standard diversion are as 4.86 and 6.04 the 't' value is .31 (df- 28, $P>0.05$). It indicates that there exist

no significant difference between Personality pattern of Anxiety and Low and Average Socio-economic group.

In the Nowboicha Block of Lakhimpur district, a sample of 3 Low socio-economic group and 14 sample of Average socio-economic group, the Mean score of Personality Pattern of Extroversion Introversion are as 42.67 and 37.21 with standard diversion are as 13.05 and 6.01. The calculated 't' value is 1.16 (df- 15, $P>0.05$). It indicate that there is no significant different between Personality pattern of Extroversion introversion with Low and Average Socio-economic group.

The Mean score of Personality Pattern of Self Concept are as 37.00 and 37.14 with standard diversion are as 6.24 and 6.38 the calculated 't' value is .03 (df- 15, $P>0.05$).. It indicate that there is significant different between Personality pattern of Self Concept and Low and Average Socio-economic group.

The Mean score of Personality Pattern of Dependent Independent are as 49.33 and 42.43 with standard diversion are as 6.02 and 9.12 the 't' value is 1.23 and $P<0.05$. It indicates that there exist no significant difference between personality pattern of Dependent Independent and Low and Average Socio-economic group.

The Mean Score of Personality Pattern of Temperament are as 46.67 and 36.00 with standard diversion are as 8.96 and 8.01 the 't' value is 2.05 (df- 15, $P>0.05$).. It indicates that there exist no significant difference between personality pattern of Temperament and Low and Average Socio-economic Group.

The Mean score of Personality Pattern of Adjustment are as 50.33 and 49.36 with standard diversion are as 8.62 and 6.22 the 't' value is .23 (df- 15, $P>0.05$).. It indicates that there is no significance difference Low and Average Socio-economic group.

The Mean score of Personality Pattern of Anxiety are as 40.33 and 38.36 with standard diversion are as .57 and 5.13 the 't' value is .64 (df- 15, $P>0.05$).

It indicates that there exist no significant difference between Personality pattern of Anxiety and Low and Average Socio-economic environment group.

In the Narayanpur Block of Lakhimpur district, a sample of 4 Low socio-economic group and 35 sample of Average socio-economic group, the Mean score of Personality Pattern of Extroversion Introversion are as 48.00 and 39.85 with standard diversion are as 9.23 and 4.01 The calculated 't' value is 2.60 (df- 15, $P>0.05$).. It indicate that there is no significant different between Personality pattern of Extroversion introversion with Low and Average Socio-economic environment group.

The Mean score of Personality Pattern of Self Concept are as 43.50 and 37.08 with standard diversion are as 9.81 and 4.25 the calculated 't' value is 1.93 and $P>0.05$.

It indicate that there is no significant different between Personality pattern of Self Concept and Low and Average Socio-economic group.

The Mean score of Personality Pattern of Dependent Independent are as 48.00 and 43.00 standard diversion are as 8.08, 6.21, the 't' value is 1.31 (df- 15, $P>0.05$).. It indicates there exist no significant difference between personality pattern of Dependent Independent and Low and Average Socio-economic group.

The Mean Score of Personality Pattern of Temperament are as 39.50 and 41.23 with standard diversion are as 5.19 and 4.16 the 't' value is .68 and $P<0.05$. It indicates that there exist no

significant difference between personality pattern of Temperament and Low and Average Socio-economic Group.

The Mean score of Personality Pattern of Adjustment are as 53.50 and 47.85 with standard diversion are as 4.04 and 6.81 the 't' value is 1.55 and v. It indicates that there is no significance difference Low and Average Socio-economic group.

The Mean score of Personality Pattern of Anxiety are as 41.50 and 37.38 with standard diversion are as .57 and 4.55 the 't' value is 1.76 (df- 15, P>0.05).. It indicates that there exist no significant difference between Personality pattern of Anxiety and Low and Average Socio-economic group.

Table -3 .3Influence of cultural and socio-economic background on personality pattern of Mishng Adolescents in Lakhimpur district (Block-wise)

Personality Pattern	Socio-Economic	Karunabari Block (N= Average-24 High-45)					Bihpuria Block (N= Average-22 High-52)					NowboichaBlock (N= Average -14 High-30)					Narayanpur Block (N= Average -13 High-35)				
		Mean	sd	t	df	Sig (2 tail)	Mean	sd	T	df	Sig (2 tail)	Mean	sd	t	df	Sig (2 tail)	Mean	sd	t	df	Sig (2 tail)
Extroversion	Average	36.63	9.47	1.59	67	.11	38.45	4.09	.77	72	.44	37.21	6.01	1.27	42	.20	39.85	4.01	.69	46	.48
	High	39.98	7.66				39.27	4.17				40.90	9.93				38.69	5.44			
Introversion	Average	39.58	8.37	1.91	67	.05	37.41	4.36	1.48	72	.14	37.14	6.38	.99	42	.32	37.08	4.25	1.61	46	.11
	High	43.38	7.52				39.08	4.45				39.70	8.52				39.23	4.06			
Self Concept	Average	40.50	3.81	4.08	67	.00	46.18	5.31	.38	72	.70	42.43	9.12	2.85	42	.00	43.00	6.21	2.12	46	.03
	High	46.36	6.43				45.54	6.99				50.47	8.50				47.20	6.05			
Dependent	Average	40.50	7.13	1.44	67	.15	39.50	6.19	1.42	72	.15	36.00	8.00	1.17	42	.24	41.23	4.16	.05	46	.95
	High	42.98	6.58				41.75	6.21				39.10	8.16				41.31	5.20			
Independent	Average	44.08	5.09	1.74	67	.08	50.77	4.70	1.04	72	.29	49.36	6.22	.60	42	.54	47.85	6.81	1.77	46	.08
	High	46.98	7.20				49.00	7.32				50.73	7.36				51.71	6.67			
Temperament	Average	39.04	8.76	1.17	67	.24	38.23	6.04	.01	72	.98	38.36	5.18	.63	42	.52	37.38	4.55	1.05	46	.29
	High																				

	High	41.44	7.70				38.25	4.14				39.60	6.39				38.86	4.18			
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Significant level is at $P < 0.05$

It is observed from the table no 3.3 in the Karunabari Block of Lakhimpur district, 24 respondents followed by Average Socio economic groups and 45 sample of High Socio economic group with the personality pattern of Extroversion Introversion, Mean score are 36.63 and 39.98 as standard diversions is 9.47 and 7.66, The calculated 't' value is 1.59 (df- 67, $P > 0.05$).

It shows that there is no significant difference between Personality pattern of Extroversion Introversion and Average socio economic group and High socio economics group.

The no respondents followed by self-concept and Average with 39.58 mean score and standard diversion is 43.38. The calculated 't' value is 1.91 (df- 15, $P > 0.05$). It indicate that there is no significant different between Personality pattern of Self Concept and Average and High Socio economic group.

The Mean score of personality pattern of Dependent Independent are as 40.50 and 46.36 with standard diversion are as 3.81 and 6.43 the 't' value is 4.08 (df- 15, $P > 0.05$).

It indicates that there exist no significant difference between personality pattern of Dependent Independent and Average and High Socio -economic group.

The Mean Score of Personality Pattern of Temperament are as 40.50 and 42.98 with standard diversion are as 7.13 and 6.58 the 't' value is 1.44 (df- 15, $P > 0.05$). It indicates that there exist no significant difference between personality pattern of Temperament and average and High Socio -economic Group.

The Mean score of Personality Pattern of Adjustment are as 44.08 and 46.98 with standard diversion are as 5.09 and 7.20 the 't' value is 1.47 (df- 15, $P > 0.05$). It indicates that there is no significance difference average and High Socio -economic Group.

The Mean score of Personality pattern of Anxiety are as 39.04 and 41.44 with standard diversion are as 8.76 and 7.70 the 't' value is 1.17 (df- 15, $P > 0.05$). It indicates that there exist no significant difference between Personality pattern of Anxiety and Average and high Socio -economic Group.

In the Bihpuria Block of Lakhimpur district, a sample of 22 Low socio-economic groups and 52 sample of Average socio-economic group, the Mean score of Personality pattern of Extroversion Introversion are as 38.45 and 39.27 with standard diversion are as 4.09 and 4.17 The calculated 't' value is .77 (df- 72, $P > 0.05$) It indicate that there is no significant different between Personality pattern of Extroversion introversion with Average and High Socio-economic group.

The Mean score of Personality Pattern of Self Concept are as 37.41 and 39.08 with standard diversion are as 4.36 and 4.45 the calculated 't' value is 1.48 (df- 72, $P > 0.05$).

It shows that there is no significant different between Personality pattern of Self Concept and Average and High Socio-economic group.

The Mean score of personality pattern of Dependent Independent are as 46.18 and 45.58 standard diversion are as 5.31 and 6.99 the 't' value is .38 (df- 72, $P > 0.05$). It indicates that there exist no significant difference between personality pattern of Dependent Independent and Average and High Socio-economic group.

The Mean Score of Personality Pattern of Temperament are as 39.50 and 41.75 with standard diversion are as 6.19 and 2.21 and 't' value is 1.42 (df- 72, $P>0.05$). It indicates that there significant difference between personality pattern of Temperament and Average and High Socio-economic Group. The Mean score of Personality Pattern of Adjustment are as 50.77 and 49.00 with standard diversion are as 4.70 and 7.32 the 't' value is 1.04 (df- 72, $P>0.05$). It indicates that there is no significance difference Average and High Socio-economic group.

The Mean score of Personality pattern of Anxiety are as 38.23 and 38.25 with standard diversion are as 6.04 and 4.14 the 't' value is .01 (df- 72, $P>0.05$) 05. It indicates that there exist significant difference between Personality pattern of Anxiety and Average and High Socio-economic group.

In the Nowboicha Block of Lakhimpur district, a sample of 14 Average socio-economic group and 30 sample of High socio-economic group, the Mean score of Personality Pattern of Extroversion Introversion are as 37.21 and 40.90 with standard diversion are as 6.01 and 9.93. The calculated 't' value is 1.27 (df- 42, $P>0.05$). It indicate that there is no significant different between Personality pattern of Extroversion introversion with Average and High Socio-economic group.

The Mean score of Personality Pattern of Self Concept are as 37.14 and 39.70 with standard diversion are as 6.38 and 8.54 the calculated 't' value is .99 (df- 42, $P>0.05$).. It indicate that there is significant different between Personality pattern of Self Concept and Average and High Socio-economic group.

The Mean score of Personality Pattern of Dependent Independent are as 42.43 and 50.47 with standard diversion are as 9.12 and 8.52 the 't' value is 2.85 and $P<0.05$. It indicates that there exist no significant difference between personality pattern of Dependent Independent and Average and High Socio-economic group.

The Mean Score of Personality Pattern of Temperament are as 36.00 and 39.10 with standard diversion are as 8.01 and 8.17 and 't' value is 1.17 (df- 42, $P>0.05$)

It shows that there exist no significant difference between personality pattern of Temperament and Average and High Socio-economic Group.

The Mean score of Personality Pattern of Adjustment are as 49.36 and 50.73 with standard diversion are as 6.22 and 7.36 the 't' value is .60 (df- 42, $P>0.05$).. It indicates that there is no significance difference Average and High Socio-economic group.

The Mean score of Personality Pattern of Anxiety are as 38.36 and 39.60 with standard diversion are as 5.13 and 6.39 the 't' value is .63 (df- 42, $P>0.05$).. It indicates that there exist no significant difference between Personality pattern of Anxiety and Average and High Socio-economic environment group.

In the Narayanpur Block of Lakhimpur district, a sample of 13 Low socio-economic group and 35 sample of Average socio-economic group, the Mean score of Personality Pattern of Extroversion Introversion are as 39.85 and 38.69 with standard diversion are as 4.08 and 5.44 The calculated 't' value is 6.99 (df- 46, $P>0.05$) It indicate that there is no significant different between Personality pattern of Extroversion introversion with Average and High Socio-economic environment group.

4. FINDING AND CONCLUSION:

It was found that there is no Influence in between Low and High cultural and socio-economic background on personality pattern of Mishng Adolescents in Lakhimpur District.

But there is significant difference between Low and Average socio-economic background on Temperament and self-concept Personality patterns in Bihpuria as well as Nowaboicha Block. High and Average of socio-economic background has significantly relationship with anxiety Personality patterns in Bihpuria Block.

The rate of savings of the Mishing families is not encouraging. All disserver households are found in the lower and middle income groups and their income is not more than RS.20, 000 per annum. However, some of the educated families of lower and middle income groups have significant savings and investment. But in general, income, investment rate is not significant

The Doburism (Animism) is the original religion of the Mishing. The most of the Mishing families follows Doubrism. More than 91% of the families follows Doubrism, about 7% follow Neo-Vaisnavism and only 0.83% is Christians.

- I. The Mishing adolescence follows the High Traditional Culture.
- II. The Cultural background is equal of IXth & Xth standard Boys and girls of Mishing adolescent in Lakhimpur District.

5. SUGGESTION FOR FURTHER RESEARCH:-

The finding of the study on **Influence of Cultural and Socio-Economic Background on Personality Pattern of Mishing Adolescents in Lakhimpur Districts of Assam**. Is also relevant to the other community. The further research on this aspect is necessary for finding out the multidimensional problems.

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